

Reg. No. : 141 / 2004

ISSN 0973 - 8762

ANUŚĪLANA

**Research Journal of Indian
Cultural, Social & Philosophical Stream**

Year: 7

2011

Volume XXXVI

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ISSN 0973 – 8762

ANUŚĪLANA – A Refereed Journal, Published Bi Monthly.

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Technical advisor
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Printed by
Kabara Offsets, Ravindrapuri, Varanasi.

E-mail : anushilana@rediffmail.com

Published by
Manvi Seva Samiti®

A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO THE COMMODITY TRADING IN INDIA

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After a long time India has experienced the commodity trading at a time when its people has forgot the trading process with a very low interest gaining a good pace after ten years of its introduction. It is necessary to thus introduce the new generation with the modern commodity trading mechanism. This paper in short aims at introducing three points: what commodity trading means; where it takes place i.e. Commodity exchanges, and, how is it regulated in the Indian economy.

Keywords: *Commodity Trading, Commodity Exchanges, Trading Mechanism.*

Introduction : Commodity trading has been a topic of controversies since a long time. However, it is marked that commodity trading in India started in an organised form in the nineteenth century with the establishment of the Bombay Cotton Association Limited in the year 1875. When we talk about commodity trading, it is also noticeable that the origin of commodity derivatives market in India backs to thousands of years ago. This existence has been referred to in the Kautilya's Arthashastra. The commodity trading in India has never been regular. It was almost banned for fifty years for a variety of reasons.

Discussing the commodity trading, calls for the conceptualisation of futures contract. A Futures contract is a standardized contract to buy or sell a specified commodity of a standardized quality in a certain date in future, at a market determined price which is known as the future price. The price is determined by the equilibrium between the forces of supply and demand among competing buy and sells orders at the exchange at the time of the purchase or sale of the contract. Another related term in the commodity trading is the options contract. An option contract gives the option holder the right, but not obligation, to purchase or sell a specific quantity of a commodity at a specific price on or before a specified date. However, both these terms come under a major head known as derivatives which means a financial contract whose value depends upon (or is derived from) the price of another asset. The use of derivatives helps the person to reduce or eliminate risks which may arise in the future. Trading in futures and options not only help in hedging the risk but also gives an opportunity for investment to the speculators who are ready to bear risk in order to get some more return.

Commodity Exchanges in India : A commodity exchange is an exchange where various commodities and derivatives products are traded. Most commodity markets across the world trade in agricultural products and other raw materials (like wheat, barley, sugar, maize, cotton, cocoa, coffee, milk products, pork bellies, oil, metals, etc.) and contracts based on them. These contracts can include spot prices, forwards, futures and options on futures. Some of the major commodity exchanges which have been set up for the effective running of the commodities trading in India can be noted as below:

The National Multi-Commodity Exchange of India Limited (NCME) was the first exchange to be granted perpetual recognition by the government. It was established in November, 2002 with 24 commodities allowed for trading.

The National Commodity and Derivatives Exchange Limited (NCDEX) is a public limited company established on 23rd April, 2003 under the Companies Act, 1956. It is the only commodity exchange in India which has been promoted by national level institutions such as ICICI Bank Limited, Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC), National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), and National Stock Exchange of India Limited (NSE) and facilitates trading in 57 commodities categorized into three groups viz; agriculture, metals and energy.

Regulation of the Indian Commodity Exchanges : The commodity trading in India is regulated by the Forward Markets Commission set up under the Forward Contracts (Regulations) Act, 1952 and overseen by the Ministry of Consumer Affairs and Public Distribution, Government of India. The department of Consumer Affairs, under this ministry, is the apex regulatory body governing all commodity exchanges in India. To study the overall supervision of the commodity trading in India, we need to cover the following:

A. The Forward Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1952, a Central Act, governs commodity derivatives trading in India. The Act defines various forms of contract. The Act envisages a three-tier regulation:

Exchange: The exchange which organizes forward trading in regulated commodities can prepare its own Articles of Association, Rules and Regulations, byelaws and regulate trading on a day to day basis.

FMC (Forward Markets Commission): The commission approves the rules and byelaws of the exchange and provides a regulatory oversight. It also acquires concurrent powers of regulation while approving the rules and byelaws or by making such rules and byelaws under the delegated powers.

Central Government: Ministry of Consumer affairs and Public Distribution under the Govt. of India is the ultimate regulatory authority. Only those associations, which are granted recognition by the Government, are allowed to organize forward trading in regulated commodities. Government has the power to suspend trading, call for information nominate directors on the Boards of the Exchanges; supersede Board of Directors of the Exchange etc. central Govt. has delegated most of these powers of FMC.

B. Forward Markets Commission (FMC) regulates commodity futures trading in India. It is statutory body set up under the Ministry of Consumer Affairs and Public Distribution in 1953 under the Forward Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1952. As per the Forward Contracts (Regulation) Act 1952, the functions of the FMC are

- a) To advise the Central Government in respect of the recognition of or the withdrawal of recognition from any association or in respect of any other matter arising out of the administration of this Act
- b) To keep forward markets under observation and to take such action in relation to them as it may consider necessary, in exercise of the powers assigned to it by or under this Act
- c) To collect and whenever the Commission thinks it necessary publish information regarding the trading condition in respect of goods to which any of the provisions of this Act is made applicable, including information regarding supply, demand and prices, and to submit to the Central Government periodical reports on the operation of this Act and on the working of forward markets relating to such goods
- d) To make recommendation generally with a view to improving the organization and working of forward markets
- e) To undertake the inspection of the accounts and other documents of (any recognized association or registered association or any member of such association) whenever it considers it necessary, and

- f) To perform such other duties and exercise such other powers as may be assigned to the Commission by or under this Act, or as may be prescribed.

To, inculcate the best practices and to promote financial integrity, market integrity and transparency into our trade FMC has imposed some regulations on the commodity exchange like Daily mark to market margining, Time stamping of trades, Novation of contracts and creation of trade / settlement guarantee fund, Bank office computerization for the existing single commodity Exchange and online trading for the new Exchanges, and Demutualization for the new Exchanges.

C. Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956 governs and regulates transaction in securities. The functions of The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) are regulating the business and any other securities market; performing such functions and exercising such powers under the provisions of Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act 1956, as may be delegated to it by the Central Government, levying fees or other charges; conducting research for the above purposes; and performing such other functions as may be prescribed. The role of FMC in the commodities markets is similar to the role of SEBI in the stock markets. The major area of difference is that while the SEBI is required to conduct research into the different areas relating to the stock exchanges and the securities market, the FMC is required to collect and publish information regarding supply, demand and prices of commodities. The finance ministry has recently amended two main clauses of the Securities Contracts (Regulation) Rules, 1957 of the Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act 1956, which would substantially widen participation in commodity futures market. Through a notification issued in August 2003, the ministry has amended rule 8 (1) (f) of the SC (R) Rules, 1957 that permits stock brokers to trade in commodity derivatives also. However, stock brokers will be permitted to trade in commodity derivatives only through a separate subsidiary that meets all the requisite norms set out by the Forward Markets Commission (FMC), the commodity futures market regulator. Further, to allow banks and other entities, the notification indicates that rule 8 (4) also has been amended to permit banks under the second schedule of the Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934 and other entities, like the Export Import (EXIM) Bank of India, National Bank for Agricultural and Rural Development (NABARD) and the National Housing Bank (NHB), to trade in commodity futures. Their respective statutes prevent these entities from trading in commodity futures.

Conclusion : Towards home, it can be said that a proper platform for trading in commodities in India has been organised and the interested

investors must learn about the know-how for the trading mechanism before playing into the market. It will definitely help them in mitigating risk. The regulatory provisions for the commodity trading process comparatively very good and it surely assures the investor's interest provided they act smartly. The growth of the commodity market acclaims that as the stock markets blooms in the Indian market, the commodity market will also. One day definitely the commodity will become the most favourable thing for the investors to invest into.

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